

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE CHOICE OF DESIGN IN ORTHOPEDIC TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH PERIODONTAL DISEASE

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Abstract

The main forms of periodontal disease are superficial lesions of the gums - gingivitis and deeper - periodontitis. Periodontitis has synonyms: alveolar pyorrhea, periodontitis, periodontosis, periodontoclasia, alveoloclasia, Fauchard's disease, etc. In 1983, the plenum of the All-Union Scientific Society of Dentists adopted a classification that is currently widely used in the CIS countries. In accordance with it, the initial form of periodontitis is gingivitis, which is an inflammation of the gums, caused by the adverse effects of general and local factors, occurring without violating the integrity of the gingival junction.

The main role in the occurrence of periodontal diseases is played by microorganisms included in the "red complex" BANA +: *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Treponema denticola*, *Tannerella forsythia*. With the simultaneous identification of these types, one can judge a high risk of developing periodontal diseases. Purpose - to determine the frequency of occurrence of various types and topography of dentition defects in patients with varying degrees of severity of periodontal disease, to establish a relationship between the severity of periodontal disease and the species number of representatives of periodontopathogenic microflora.

Keywords: periodontitis, periodontopathogenic microflora, PCR diagnostics, orthopedic treatment planning

Examination of a patient with periodontal pathology allows not only to correctly diagnose the disease, its severity, and clinical course, but also to determine the etiological factors and pathogenetic mechanisms of the inflammatory or dystrophic process in the periodontium. In this case, it is possible to clarify the role of genetic factors, the influence of nutrition, ecology, occupational hazards, etc.

All these examination results form the basis for drawing up an adequate, comprehensive treatment plan using the means of etiotropic, pathogenetic and symptomatic therapy. To predict and plan the complex treatment of periodontal diseases, it is first necessary to identify the etiological factors that predispose to the development of inflammatory changes in periodontal tissues. Achievements in the field of cultivation and study of dental plaque bacteria, identification of differences in the structure of plaques in normal and pathological conditions formed the basis for the search for specific causes of periodontitis [7]. In accordance with the so-called "specific plaque hypothesis", which was formulated in the mid-1970s, the pathogenicity of a plaque depends on the presence or relative predominance of specific microbes in it, and destructive periodontitis is a consequence of the process initiated by them [5]. The adoption of a specific hypothesis was facilitated by the fact that *A. actinomycetemcomitans* was named as the

main causative agent of localized aggressive periodontitis. The concept of biofilms has changed approaches to diseases in various fields of medicine: taking into account new data, the concepts of pathogenesis are being revised [6]. In the development of periodontal diseases, an important role is played by such etiological factors as previous and concomitant diseases, heredity, bad habits (smoking), vitamin deficiency, social factors (stress) [2]. Currently, traumatic occlusion is also referred to as an etiological factor in the development of periodontal diseases. Its appearance is facilitated by factors such as a reduction in the number of pairs of antagonistic teeth, deformation of the dentition, anomalies of individual teeth, dentition and bite, prosthetics with bridges and the use of clasp systems of removable dentures. According to WHO, a high level of periodontal disease is observed at the age of 35 to 44 years (65-98%). It is noteworthy that it is in this age category of patients that factors appear that predispose to the occurrence of recurrent occlusal trauma, which, in turn, provokes the development of periodontal diseases [3, 4]. Since the main etiological factors in the development of periodontal diseases are the microflora of the oral cavity and traumatic occlusion, the analysis of the clinical picture and X-ray examination data allows us to make a differential diagnosis between the forms of traumatic occlusion, justify complex treatment and give recommendations to the patient on caring for the oral

cavity after orthopedic treatment [1]. Currently, about 530 species of microorganisms have been identified that live in supragingival and subgingival plaque [10]. A little more than ten are classified as periodontopathogenic, most of them are gram-negative. Obligate anaerobes include *Porphyromonas endodontalis*, *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Treponema denticola*, *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *Tannerella forsythia*. Facultative anaerobes are represented by *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans* [8]. The main role in the occurrence of periodontal diseases is played by microorganisms included in the "red complex" BANA +: *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Treponema denticola*, *Tannerella forsythia*. With the simultaneous identification of these types, one can judge a high risk of developing periodontal diseases. (BANA is a test for the detection of bacteria containing trypsin-like peptidase, which hydrolyzes the synthetic peptide N-a-Benzoyl-DL-arginin-2-naphthylamide (BANA)) [9]. In the periodontal tissues with partial loss of teeth during the chewing function, a functional stress occurs that exceeds the physiological one, which, to a certain extent, will be compensated by the corresponding tissue and vascular reactions of the periodontium. In the future, excessive stretching of the periodontal fibers occurs, which leads to bone resorption and a violation of the position of the tooth. This is the so-called compensated functional overload. With traumatic occlusion, cell damage and the release of lysosomal enzymes, chemical mediators, and collagenase activators occur. Mediators increase vascular permeability, enzymes damage the vascular endothelium, causing tissue exudation and edema, and collagenase destroys fibers [8]. If traumatic occlusion is eliminated, phagocytes absorb the remains of destroyed tissues, fibroblasts again synthesize glycoproteins and collagen fibers, and tissues heal [3]. Purpose - to determine the frequency of occurrence of various types and topography of dentition defects in patients with varying degrees of severity of periodontal disease, to establish a relationship between the severity of periodontal disease and the species number of representatives of periodontopathogenic microflora.

Methodology

A clinical examination of a group of patients consisting of 30 women and 8 men in the age category from 35 to 60 years was carried out. The collection of anamnesis was carried out using a survey and filling out a special questionnaire. External examination and examination of the oral cavity made it possible to establish the clinical conditions and anatomical features that contribute to the development of periodontal diseases, namely: the type of bite, the presence of defects in the dentition, traumatic occlusion, plaque, the degree of pathological tooth mobility, bleeding gums, the depth of periodontal pockets. An analysis of 38 orthopantomograms was carried out in order to determine the level of bone tissue destruction in the area of all groups of teeth and establish a final diagnosis. Sterile paper points were used to collect the contents in the area of the deepest periodontal pockets in 4 segments of the jaws. The pins were placed in Eppendorf with a transport medium. In the microbiological laboratory of PIMU, periodontopathogenic microorganisms were

identified by PCR diagnostics and their number was measured. The test systems of the Dentoscreen kits make it possible to identify seven microorganisms associated with the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases in a clinically significant concentration. The level of risk of periodontal disease was assessed according to the manufacturer's scale. Results Based on the data of clinical and radiological examinations, patients were divided into three groups depending on the severity of periodontal disease: the first group included 7 patients with a mild degree, the second group included 14 patients with a moderate degree, and the third group included 17 patients with a severe degree. During a clinical examination, we calculated the frequency of occurrence of various kinds of dentition defects in patients with varying degrees of severity of periodontal disease. In patients with a mild degree of periodontitis, included, terminal and combined dentition defects occur with approximately the same frequency, in patients with moderate severity, combined defects are more common, and included and terminal - in 33 and 17% of cases, respectively, in patients with severe severity in 82% of cases, combined defects of the dentition were observed and in 18% - included. After analyzing the results of the PCR study, a direct correlation was established between the severity of periodontal disease and the number of representatives of periodontopathogenic microflora. In the group of patients with mild periodontitis, 65% had up to 2 representatives of pathogenic microorganisms, 35% had more than 4, in the group with moderate severity, 50% had up to 5 microorganisms, and 50% had 6 representatives, in the group with severe degree in 64% - up to 4 microorganisms and in 36% - more than 6 representatives. Moreover, the following pattern has been established: the more representatives of the "red complex" BANA + are found in a patient, the more severe the degree of periodontitis. In the group of patients with mild severity of periodontal disease in 89% of cases there are 1-2 representatives of this complex and only in 11% - 3, in the group with an average degree in 67% of patients - 1-2 representatives and in 33% - 3, in the group with a severe degree in 40% of patients - 2 representatives and in 60% - 3.

Findings

It was found that the degree of generalized periodontitis depends on the number of microorganisms causing periodontal pathology. Given the microbiological status, it is possible to rationally plan orthopedic treatment.

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